

DAYTIME SURFACE TEMPERATURES OF THE MOON DERIVED FROM HIGH-RESOLUTION IIRS ON-BOARD CHANDRAYAAN-2. Subhadyouti Bose^{1*}, Denesh Karunakaran^{1,2}, Tvisha Kapadia¹, Neha Panwar¹, Arpeet Chandane^{1,3}, and Neeraj Srivastava¹, ¹Planetary Remote Sensing Section, Planetary Sciences Division, Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad-380009, India; ²Saint Anthony Falls Laboratory, Department of Civil, Environmental and Geo-Engineering, University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, MN 55414, United States ³Department of Computer Science and Engineering – AI ML, G. H. Rasoni College of Engineering and Management, Pune – 412207, India; subha.bose.geoscience@gmail.com

Introduction: The Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) launched its second mission to the Moon on-board Chandrayaan-2 on 22 July 2019, which carried one of the most advanced imaging spectrometers – the Imaging Infra-Red Spectrometer (IIRS) [1]. IIRS is the first lunar spectrometer that can operate in the extended wavelength range of 0.7 μm to 5 μm with a spatial resolution of ~ 80 m/pixel, which is attained from a nearly constant altitude of ~ 100 km on a polar circular orbit. In this study, we have used multiple IIRS images and data derived from a thermal model [2] spanning different latitudes, times of acquisition, and terrain types to obtain a robust and reliable correlation between the derived surface temperatures.

Study areas: Eighteen IIRS images, acquired between $\sim 08:00$ and $\sim 16:30$ hours local time, have been analysed in this work, with the image extents stretching between the latitudes of $\sim 67^\circ$ N up to $\sim 73^\circ$ S, thereby covering a wide range of latitudes across the lunar surface (Fig. 1). One of the 16 images stretches from $\sim 44^\circ$ N to $\sim 44^\circ$ S and includes an area that passes through highlands to the north of Mare Crisium, as well as the highlands to the south of Mare Fecunditatis. The particularly large extent of the image allows us to study temperature variations across a wide range of latitudes as well as different types of surfaces. The justification behind selecting these images is to showcase the variation of surface temperatures as a function of terrain types, latitudes, and times of data acquisition.

Fig. 1: Surface temperature images derived from the sixteen IIRS strips used in this study have been overlaid on an LRO-WAC global mosaic

Data and methods: Calibrated IIRS Level-1 (CODMAC Level 3, NASA PDS L1B) radiance data have been used in this study. Each IIRS pixel is radiometrically corrected, band-separated, dark corrected, and provide band-to-band registered surface radiance (SI unit: $\text{W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{Sr } \mu\text{m})$). Each IIRS image was manually seleno-referenced to their actual Ground Control Points by performing a rigorous image-to-image seleno-referencing with LRO-WAC as the reference image. The IIRS images selected in this study were captured at different local times of a lunar day. This was done with an aim to check the various temperature trends across different lunar local times. The radiance pixels from all the images were converted to surface temperatures by inverting the Planck blackbody function and by assuming a constant emissivity value ($\epsilon = 0.95$) for all the images. Surface temperatures derived from IIRS have been compared with those from a lunar thermal model [2].

Results:

Analysis of surface temperatures derived from IIRS and the thermal model: Our analysis of the IIRS dataset (images obtained between the lunar local times of $\sim 08:00$ and $\sim 16:30$ hours) reveals that the mean temperature differences (obtained by subtracting the IIRS temperature means from the corresponding model-derived temperature means for each image) are the highest towards the early morning (prior to $\sim 09:30$ hours) as well as later in the day (after $\sim 14:00$ hours) on the Moon (Fig. 2). Based on this analysis, we were able to identify a block of time during which the mean differences between IIRS and model-derived temperature data were comparatively less. The mean difference varied between 0.69 K – 23.9 K between $\sim 09:30$ and $\sim 14:00$ hours on the lunar surface. Therefore, the local lunar times of $\sim 09:30$ to $\sim 14:00$ hours represent the optimum time range during which the temperatures estimated from IIRS would be the most reliable and comparable to the corresponding model-derived temperature data. During these local times, the Sun remains at a sufficient angle above the lunar surface ($< 40^\circ$) [3], which allows IIRS to accumulate sufficient thermally emitted signal in the spectral range of 4.5 to 5 μm . Beyond these times, however, a large deviation between IIRS and model-derived temperatures is recorded, due to the non-optimum solar illumination conditions.

To analyse the differences between the model-derived and observed temperatures, we used 9 IIRS images such that they were acquired within our proposed time frame. The temperatures estimated from IIRS were compared with the model using two different criteria – (i) at every 10° latitude we compared IIRS-derived mean temperature against the model-derived temperature across an entire lunar day, and (ii) at a fixed local time (IIRS image acquisition time) and over latitude bins of $1^\circ (\pm 0.5^\circ)$, we plotted IIRS data pixels from within that bin. From the population of pixels of an entire IIRS image, we have selected a small sample of pixels ($\sim 80,000$ to $\sim 100,000$) within a $\pm 0.5^\circ$ latitudinal range around each specific latitude and then calculated the mean for that range. For every corresponding latitudinal bin of IIRS, temperatures were also estimated from the thermal model at every 0.5° latitude. To better describe the goodness of fit between the temperatures obtained from IIRS and the thermal model, pixels sampled from IIRS images along with their mean (dashed red line) were plotted across the different latitudes and were overlaid by the values retrieved from the thermal model at latitudinal intervals of 0.5° (solid yellow line). The estimated temperatures fell within the 2σ bounds, which ensured the statistical significance of this data. This comparison allowed us to analyse the temperature variations observed in real time from IIRS caused by differences in latitude, lunar local time, topography, and solar incidence angle at a higher spatial resolution.

1 - 08:00, 2 - 08:32, 3 - 09:28, 4 - 10:21, 5 - 11:06, 6 - 11:49, 7 - 13:02, 8 - 13:05, 9 - 13:10, 10 - 13:33, 11 - 13:49, 12 - 14:32, 13 - 14:32, 14 - 16:00, 15 - 16:01, 16 - 16:22

Fig. 2: A plot showing the absolute differences between the mean temperatures obtained from IIRS and the thermal model, which was run as per the acquisition times of IIRS. A time-block extending from $\sim 09:30$ hours up to $\sim 14:00$ hours, during which the calculated absolute mean differences are relatively smaller, is shown in blue.

By analysing the IIRS data, we found the temperature differences between the model and the observed dataset to be in line with the expected trends for the lunar surface. However, at a few latitudes (between 0° to 20° and between -10° and -30°), some anomalous differences have been noted

that can be identified from the figures. In these cases, the mean of the modeled temperature exceeds the 2σ range of the sampled pixels, which could be attributed to local topography, solar incidence angles, regolith properties, unusual albedo/emissivity properties of the crater walls/floors, and anisotropic thermal emissions from rough, sunlit surfaces [4]. The absolute differences obtained between the thermal model and IIRS data between the latitudes of $\pm 60^\circ$ have been shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Comparison of IIRS and model-derived temperatures between the latitudes of 60 to -60 at 13:02 to 13:49 hours local lunar time. The green line indicates the model-derived temperature, while the blue line indicates the IIRS-derived temperatures obtained at a coordinated time for both the datasets. The absolute errors have been shown with a red dotted line.

In conclusion, the results obtained in this study bring out the potential of using IIRS data for estimating the day time surface temperatures across the lunar surface at a high spatial resolution. Also, for the first time, a comparison between a thermal model and IIRS data has been shown in this study, which strengthens the reliability and robustness of the IIRS data within the suggested time frame. We propose that the surface temperatures measured by IIRS could be used to further understand the lunar thermal environment at a high spatial resolution.

References: [1] Chowdhury, A.R. (2020) *Curr. Sci*, 118, 368–375. [2] Hayne et al. (2017) *JGR*, 122, 2371-2400. [3] Williams et al., (2017) *Icarus*, 283, 300-325. [4] Paige et al. (2010) *Science*, 330, 479-482.